

AGRICULTURAL ECONOMY

¹Jaksimova Zukhra Rustem kizi, ²Abishov Mukhammed

¹Student of Karakalpakstan Institute of Agriculture and Agrotechnologies

²Candidate of Economical Sciences, Associated Professor, Karakalpak State University

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7708882>

Abstract. *The article provides information about agricultural economics and management, how to manage it, and the development of agricultural economics and its in-depth study. Bringing them to the level of demand theoretically and practically is not only for agricultural economics, but also for other economics is also important for species.*

Keywords: *economy, structure, reform, network, resource, investment, income, profit, solution, task.*

The agricultural sector is very important in the economy of our country. Because half of the population of our republic lives in rural areas, and the well-being of the people is inextricably linked with the development of this sector. In addition, the agricultural sector plays a significant role in the gross domestic product and foreign exchange earnings of our country. The agricultural sector is important in providing the population with food products and raw materials for some industries. Now, the growth of the population and needs, as well as the growth of the processing industry, objectively require the further increase in the production of agricultural products. That is why it is necessary to develop and improve the effectiveness of this network.

Our first President Islam Karimov noted that the achievements in the agricultural sector are extremely important for the economic development of our country, "Today our society has realized that improving our lives, raising the standard of living of the population, increasing the efficiency of our economy, feeding our people, planning our future, in short, what kind of problem, what kind of issue do we see? "Let's face it, most of our wealth is primarily related to agriculture. The sector that feeds us all is agriculture".

In order to develop agriculture at the level of the requirements of the laws of the market economy, deepening, improving, and investing in the theoretical and methodological foundations of various forms of ownership that have the opportunity to operate freely in the network, the types of entrepreneurship based on them, and the free market relations between them. attract and introduce scientific and technical achievements, new techniques and advanced technologies into production, clearly define the ways of full and effective use of limited land and water resources, capital and labor resources in the short and long term, save at all costs, increase labor productivity It is appropriate to determine ways to increase the amount of profit on the basis of promotion, improvement of the employee-employee incentive system. It is necessary to take into account the specific features of agriculture when creating, developing, and introducing the scientific and practical foundations of these issues into production. It is necessary to take into account the laws of the free market economy, the nature, causes and consequences of all relations, the specific characteristics of the agricultural sector in the study of "Agricultural Economy". The agricultural network has the following specific features:

a) the influence of the natural factor is strong in agriculture. Temperature, precipitation, wind and other natural factors affect the production process in the network;

b) land is the main means of production in agriculture. Compared to other branches, feed is very important in agricultural production, because the production process in this branch is carried out directly on the ground. A seed is sown on the ground and a crop is grown on the ground. There are specific characteristics of land use, the denial or insufficient attention to which will lead to negative consequences;

d) agricultural production is carried out on very large areas. This, in turn, creates a certain demand in the organization of production;

e) production in the agricultural sector is seasonal. Crops and livestock require the passage of the entire vegetation period in the production of crops. This situation leads to a significant increase in the difference between the duration of expenses and income from activities in the network. For example, in cotton production, the production process begins in early spring and ends in autumn. In addition, the seasonality of production requires the organization of effective use of available resources in the network throughout the year. It is necessary to develop other forms of entrepreneurship in the network in order to provide employment to labor resources in the winter months;

f) living organisms also participate as labor tools in the production process. Specialists working in the field of agriculture must know the biological and zoological characteristics of plants and animals, and take them into account in the production process. The effectiveness of labor spent in agriculture largely depends on the biological capabilities of plants and livestock;

g) a part of the agricultural produce is used in the network itself for seed, fodder, food and other purposes. requires painting. During the rest of the year, this capacity is relatively empty.

In summary we can say that the agricultural sector is important in the economy of Uzbekistan. It supplies the population with food products, and the processing industry with raw materials. In order to improve the country's economy in the future, the development of agriculture is an objective necessity. As a result of agrarian-economic reforms implemented in agriculture, forms of collective, private and mixed ownership are gradually established and continuously developed. Farmers and peasant farms and other forms of entrepreneurship are being organized and developed on the basis of private ownership. In agriculture, special attention is being paid to the introduction of forms of economic management that ensure the material interests of farmers and awaken in them a sense of real ownership. property and the form of economic management based on it have also been preserved. In the future, it is desirable to increase the attention to the development of enterprises based on private and joint ownership.

REFERENCES

1. Karimov I.A. Agricultural development is a source of prosperity. - T.: "Uzbekistan", 1993
2. Abduganiyev A., Abduganiyev A.A. Agricultural economy. - T.: Publishing House of the Literary Fund of the Writers' Union of Uzbekistan, 2004
3. Murtazayev O., Ismailov A.Q. Agricultural economy. - T.: Labor", 2003